

THEORETICAL DETERMINATION OF THE STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATES IN A CRACKED LAMINATE USING A MODEL OF MULTI-LAYERED MATERIALS AND VALIDATION OF A DELAMINATION CRITERION

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SUMMARY: The aim of this paper is the analytical determination of the individual strain energy release rates in a delaminated multi-layer by means of a model of plates which provides no singular stresses. The strain energy release rates are expressed as quadratic functions of the interfacial stresses at the crack tip. These expressions and pertinent delamination criteria can help predict delamination onset and growth. As an application example, data of edge delamination tests on carbon-epoxy laminates are used for determining a mode III delamination criterion involving the corresponding energy release rate. This criterion yields very accurate predictions and its analytical expression validates from an energetic point of view a maximum stress criterion proposed in an earlier paper.

KEYWORDS: Delamination; Energy release rate; Laminate; Criterion; Interfacial stresses

INTRODUCTION

Delamination is perhaps the most critical failure mode in multi-layered structures. Hence, it is necessary to predict accurately its onset and growth. For predicting delamination onset due to edge effects, some authors apply criteria involving the values of the averages of the interfacial stresses over a characteristic distance from the edge [1,2] because the exact interfacial stresses are often singular at the edges. In [3,4], a different approach is used: the authors propose a criterion involving the maximum values of the interfacial stresses evaluated by means of a model of plates called *M4-5N* [5,6] (*Multi-particle Model of Multi-layered Materials with 5 kinematic fields per layer for an N-layer laminate*) which yields finite values [7]. This criterion provides very accurate predictions of mode III delamination onset in cross-ply carbon-epoxy laminates.

Nevertheless, the criteria described above do not have an energetic foundation and may not be well adapted for predicting delamination growth. Fracture mechanics are used instead and linear elastic assumptions are usually considered. In heterogeneous multi-layers a delamination criterion based only on the total strain energy release rate is unable to predict well mixed mode delaminations [8]. The delamination criteria based on energetic considerations must involve then the individual strain energy release rates related to each fracture mode (I, II and III). However, the individual energy release rates in the case of a crack between dissimilar media do not converge [9,10] due to oscillatory singularities around the crack tip [11,12]. The use of approximate models instead of solid finite elements can help solve the problem. These models have an advantage over the solid finite elements for the calculations can be carried out even for a high number of layers and the results are easier to handle since no singularities exist [3,4,5,6,7,13,14].

The authors propose herein the model of plates *M4-5N* [6,7] for determining the analytical expressions of the individual strain energy rates in an elastic multi-layer containing a cracked interface. The model has been inspired by Pagano's work [13] and already been developed [6] and validated [5,7]. By making use of the *M4-5N* model the multi-layer becomes a superposition of Reissner plates [15] coupled by interfacial stresses. The *M4-5N* takes into account displacement discontinuities at the cracked interface and its equations are obtained by means of an adaptation of the

classical Hellinger-Reissner formulation [16] of 3D elastic problems. The model provides finite values for the interfacial stresses. The authors apply the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) [17] and express the individual strain energy release rates as quadratic functions of the interfacial stresses at the crack tip. With these analytical expressions, the opening and sliding displacements at the crack tip are not necessary to calculate the individual strain energy release rates and the single configuration of the delaminated multi-layer is to be considered (with the solid finite element technique, the application of the VCCT needs the calculation of two configurations: the open crack and the closed crack configurations). Moreover, these strain energy release rates can be calculated at delamination onset without the well known assumption and identification of an initial flaw length.

In this paper, the authors first describe the mechanical problem of the delaminated elastic multi-layer and then define the pertinent notations. Secondly, the equations of the $M4-5N$ model taking into account displacement discontinuities at the cracked interface are determined. Next, the VCCT is used to determine an analytical expression of the individual strain energy release rates involving only the interfacial stresses at the crack tip. Afterwards, as an application of this theoretical result, the experimental results with carbon-epoxy laminates in [4,18] are used in order to determine a mode III delamination criterion which predicts accurately delamination onset for the considered laminates. Lastly, as another application of the theoretical result, the authors compare the expression of the strain energy release rate criterion with that of the empirical maximum stress criterion of mode III delamination onset proposed in [3,4]; the authors conclude that the two criteria are practically equivalent from an energetic point of view.

PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND NOTATIONS

Let us consider the flat $(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_N)$ multi-layer composed of N layers of orthotropic elastic materials (see Figure 1). The laminate is subjected to a mechanical loading on its boundary; the upper and lower faces of the laminate are subjected to continuous surfacic forces. A delamination crack at the interface between layers k and $k+1$ is considered; this crack is supposed to be connected with the edge. The delamination front is assumed to be and to remain parallel to the x -axis when delamination grows. The eventual friction at the crack faces is neglected.

Figure 1. Multilayer with a delamination crack

Throughout this work,

- superscripts i and $j, j+1$ indicate layer i and the interface between layers j and $j+1$ ($1 \leq i \leq N$, $1 \leq j \leq N-1$), respectively,
- subscripts “,1”, “,2” and “,3” denote the partial derivatives with respect to x , y and z , respectively
- bold face characters define tensors, matrices and vectors
- the multi-layer lies within the volume defined by $\begin{cases} (x, y) \in \omega \\ z \in [h_-^1, h_+^N] \end{cases}$;
- layer i occupies the geometrical space defined by $\begin{cases} (x, y) \in \omega \\ z \in [h_-^i, h_+^i] \end{cases}$; its thickness is $t^i = h_+^i - h_-^i$,

- subscripts o, p, q and r indicate the components in the (x, y, z) space; they are assigned the values 1, 2 and 3,
- subscripts α, β, γ and δ indicate the components on the (x, y) plane and are assigned the values 1 and 2,
- \mathbf{U} and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ denote respectively the 3D displacement field and the 3D stress field,
- $\Gamma^{j,j+1}$ denotes the interface between layers j and $j+1$,
- $\boldsymbol{\gamma}^{k,k+1}$ denotes the first order tensor of displacement discontinuities at the cracked interface $\Gamma^{k,k+1}$ defined by the following equation:

$$\lim_{z \rightarrow h_+^k} U_o(x, y, z) - \lim_{z \rightarrow h_+^k} U_o(x, y, z) = \gamma_o^{k,k+1}(x, y), \quad (1)$$

- each layer i is orthotropic and the orthotropy directions are L_i, T_i and N_i as defined by the vectors $\mathbf{e}_{L_i} = \cos\theta_i \mathbf{e}_x + \sin\theta_i \mathbf{e}_y$, $\mathbf{e}_{T_i} = \sin\theta_i \mathbf{e}_x + \cos\theta_i \mathbf{e}_y$ and $\mathbf{e}_{N_i} = \mathbf{e}_z$
- $\mathbf{S}(x, y, z) = \mathbf{S}(z)$ denotes the 4th-order tensor of compliances; it is constant in each layer. Its components are S_{opqr} , with $S_{opqr} = 0$ in the presence of an odd number of 3 (z -direction) in the set $opqr$,
- the second-order tensors \mathbf{S}^i and \mathbf{S}_Q^i represent the in-plane and shearing compliances of layer i , respectively; they are defined by:
 $S_{\alpha\beta}^i = S_{\alpha\alpha\beta\beta}(z)$, $S_{16}^i = S_{61}^i = 2S_{1112}(z)$, $S_{26}^i = S_{62}^i = 2S_{2212}(z)$, $S_{66}^i = 4S_{1212}(z)$,
 $S_{Q\alpha\beta}^i = 4S_{\alpha 3\beta 3}(z)$ for $z \in [h_-^i, h_+^i]$. The scalar S_3^i denotes the normal compliance of layer i and is defined by: $S_3^i = S_{3333}(z)$ for $z \in [h_-^i, h_+^i]$,
- G denotes the strain energy release rate associated to the delamination crack growth. G_I, G_{II} and G_{III} denote the individual strain energy release rates related to mode I, mode II and mode III fractures, respectively.

In order to determine the individual energy release rates, the virtual crack closure method is proposed. This method requires the calculation of the stress fields and the determination of the crack opening and sliding displacements (displacement discontinuities). Herein, these stress and displacement fields are determined by means of the model of plates called *M4-5N*.

THE *M4-5N* MODEL APPLIED TO THE PROBLEM

By using the *M4-5N* model, the multi-layer (3-D object) becomes a superposition of N Reissner plates [15] (a 2-D object with N particles at each geometrical point and for each particle 5 kinematic fields are considered) coupled with interfacial stresses. This model has been inspired by Pagano's work [13] and already developed and validated [5,6,7]. In [6,7] the model is constructed for multi-layers containing the following inelastic fields: inelastic strains in the layers and displacement discontinuities at the interfaces. In the case of the delaminated multi-layer considered herein, only the displacement discontinuities at the delaminated interface are to be considered. These inelastic fields are fixed and are supposed to be known during the modelling [6,7] in all this section. Since the model has already been developed, this section applies the model equations to our problem and shows only the equations which will be used for calculating the individual strain energy release rates. The model is obtained by means of adapting [6,7] the classical Hellinger-Reissner formulation of 3-D elastic problems [16] and choosing approximate stresses. The formulation yields approximate displacements, which are consistent with the stress approximation and are discontinuous at the cracked interface as desired. Using the variational properties of the formulation [16], we obtain the model equations.

1 Approximate 3D stresses and displacements

The in-plane stress components $\sigma_{\alpha\beta}$ ($\alpha, \beta \in \{1, 2\}$) are chosen as linear functions of z and the 3D equilibrium equations lead both to shear stresses $\sigma_{\alpha 3}$ in the form of quadratic polynomials of z and to the normal stress σ_{33} as third-order polynomials. The polynomial coefficients are expressed in terms of the following generalized internal forces [5,6,7]:

- force, moment and shear resultants of layer i , respectively :

$$N_{\alpha\beta}^i(x, y) = \int_{h_-^i}^{h_+^i} \sigma_{\alpha\beta}(x, y, z) dz, \quad M_{\alpha\beta}^i(x, y) = \int_{h_-^i}^{h_+^i} (z - \bar{h}^i) \sigma_{\alpha\beta}(x, y, z) dz \quad (2)$$

$$\text{and } Q_{\alpha}^i(x, y) = \int_{h_-^i}^{h_+^i} \sigma_{\alpha 3}(x, y, z) dz$$

$$\text{where } \bar{h}^i = \frac{h_+^i + h_-^i}{2}$$

- interfacial shear and normal stresses at interfaces $\Gamma^{j, j+1}$:

$$\tau_{\alpha}^{j, j+1}(x, y) = \sigma_{\alpha 3}(x, y, h_+^j), \quad \nu^{j, j+1}(x, y) = \sigma_{33}(x, y, h_+^j). \quad (3)$$

where $(x, y) \in \omega$.

Once the approximate stresses are defined, the Hellinger-Reissner formulation helps to identify [6,7]

- the following $5N$ generalized displacements for $(x, y) \in \omega$:

$$U_{\alpha}^i(x, y) = \int_{h_-^i}^{h_+^i} \frac{1}{t^i} U_{\alpha}(x, y, z) dz, \quad \Phi_{\alpha}^i(x, y) = \int_{h_-^i}^{h_+^i} \frac{12(z - \bar{h}^i)}{t^{i3}} U_{\alpha}(x, y, z) dz, \quad (4)$$

$$U_3^i(x, y) = \int_{h_-^i}^{h_+^i} \frac{1}{t^i} U_3(x, y, z) dz$$

- the following generalized strains for $(x, y) \in \omega$:

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^i(x, y) = \frac{1}{2} (U_{\alpha, \beta}^i + U_{\beta, \alpha}^i), \quad \chi_{\alpha\beta}^i(x, y) = \frac{1}{2} (\Phi_{\alpha, \beta}^i + \Phi_{\beta, \alpha}^i), \quad (5)$$

$$d_{\Phi \alpha}^i(x, y) = \Phi_{\alpha}^i + U_{3, \alpha}^i, \quad D_{\alpha}^{j, j+1}(x, y) = U_{\alpha}^{j+1} - U_{\alpha}^j - \frac{t^j}{2} \Phi_{\alpha}^j - \frac{t^{j+1}}{2} \Phi_{\alpha}^{j+1},$$

$$\text{and } D_3^{j, j+1}(x, y) = U_3^{j+1} - U_3^j$$

- the generalized inelastic strains for $(x, y) \in \omega$:

$$\gamma_{\alpha}^{j, j+1}(x, y) \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma_3^{j, j+1}(x, y) \quad (6)$$

where $\gamma_{\alpha}^{j, j+1} = \gamma_3^{j, j+1} = 0$ if $j \neq k$ (only the interface $\Gamma^{k, k+1}$ is delaminated).

2 Model equations

Using the variational properties [16] of the formulation for a variation of the 3D displacements and consequently of the generalized displacements, one obtains the generalized $5N$ equilibrium equations and the generalized boundary conditions at the edges as shown in [5,6,7]. Lastly, in applying equations (5) and (6) and the variational properties of the formulation for a variation of the approximate stresses, one obtains the generalized elastic constitutive equations [6,7] related to:

- the in-plane force resultants and to the in-plane moment resultants in layer i ($1 \leq i \leq N$):

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^i = \frac{S_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^i}{t^i} N_{\gamma\delta}^i \quad \text{and} \quad \chi_{\alpha\beta}^i = \frac{12}{t^{i3}} S_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^i M_{\gamma\delta}^i, \quad \text{respectively} \quad (7)$$

- the out-of-plane shear resultants in layer i ($1 \leq i \leq N$):

$$d_{\Phi\alpha}^i = \frac{6}{5t^i} S_{Q\alpha\beta}^i Q_{\beta}^i - \frac{1}{10} S_{Q\alpha\beta}^i (\tau_{\beta}^{i,i+1} + \tau_{\beta}^{i-1,i}) \quad (8)$$

- the shear stresses at interface $\Gamma^{j,j+1}$ ($1 \leq j \leq N-1$)

$$D_{\alpha}^{j,j+1} - \gamma_{\alpha}^{j,j+1} = -\frac{1}{10} S_{Q\alpha\beta}^j Q_{\beta}^j - \frac{1}{10} S_{Q\alpha\beta}^{j+1} Q_{\beta}^{j+1} - \frac{t^j}{30} S_{Q\alpha\beta}^j \tau_{\beta}^{j-1,j} \\ + \frac{2}{15} (t^j S_{Q\alpha\beta}^j + t^{j+1} S_{Q\alpha\beta}^{j+1}) \tau_{\beta}^{j,j+1} - \frac{t^{j+1}}{30} S_{Q\alpha\beta}^{j+1} \tau_{\beta}^{j,j+1} \quad (9)$$

- the normal stresses at interface $\Gamma^{j,j+1}$ ($1 \leq j \leq N-1$)

$$D_3^{j,j+1} - \gamma_3^{j,j+1} = \frac{9}{70} t^j S_3^j \nu^{j-1,j} + \frac{13}{35} (t^j S_3^j + t^{j+1} S_3^{j+1}) \nu^{j,j+1} \\ + \frac{9}{70} t^{j+1} S_3^{j+1} \nu^{j+1,j+2} \quad (10)$$

where $\tau_{\alpha}^{0,1}(x,y) = -T_{\alpha}^d(x,y,h_-^1)$, $\tau_{\alpha}^{N,N+1}(x,y) = T_{\alpha}^d(x,y,h_+^N)$, $\nu^{0,1}(x,y) = -T_3^d(x,y,h_-^1)$, $\nu^{N,N+1}(x,y) = T_3^d(x,y,h_+^N)$ and $\gamma_{\alpha}^{j,j+1} = \gamma_3^{j,j+1} = 0$ if $j \neq k$. \mathbf{T}^d denotes the external surfacic force at the upper and lower faces of the multi-layer.

Now that the model equations have been recalled, the interfacial stresses can be determined in the cracked laminate for a given displacement discontinuity field $\gamma^{k,k+1}$. This field is still not known but in the next section it will be determined at the crack tip in order to obtain the expressions of the individual strain energy release rates.

STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE EXPRESSION

In all this section, the loading is fixed. The strain energy release rates are determined by means of the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) [17]. This method yields an expression of the individual strain energy release rates involving the displacement discontinuities and the interfacial stresses calculated at the crack tip. The determination of the displacement discontinuities as linear functions of the interfacial stresses provides then a second and more useful expression of the strain energy rates.

Let us first apply the VCCT technique in order to determine a first expression of the strain energy release rate. The front position is supposed to be $y = a$ and an infinitesimal crack growth da is considered. The energy that must be supplied in order to close the crack of da is [19]

$$dW = \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_{x_0(a)}^{x_1(a)} \left(\tau_1^{k,k+1}(x,a^+) \gamma_1^{k,k+1}(x,a^-) + \tau_2^{k,k+1}(x,a^+) \gamma_2^{k,k+1}(x,a^-) \right) dx \right] da \quad (11)$$

where $x_0(a)$ and $x_1(a)$ are the bounds of the delamination front on the x -axis ($x_1 - x_0$ is the length of the delamination front). The strain energy release rate for the given load is then obtained by using the following equation:

$$G = \frac{dW}{l \times da} = \int_{x_0}^{x_1} g(x) dx \quad (12)$$

where $l = x_1 - x_0$ and g is the linear density of strain energy release rate defined by:

$$g(x) = \frac{1}{2 \times l} \left(\tau_1^{k,k+1}(x,a^+) \gamma_1^{k,k+1}(x,a^-) + \tau_2^{k,k+1}(x,a^+) \gamma_2^{k,k+1}(x,a^-) \right. \\ \left. + \nu^{k,k+1}(x,a^+) \gamma_3^{k,k+1}(x,a^-) \right). \quad (13)$$

Since the $M4$ - $5N$ model yields finite stress values, the displacement discontinuities at the crack tip in the cracked zone could be not null: this reflects the interfacial stress singularity of the exact 3D

solution. In this manner, the displacement discontinuity fields $\gamma_o^{k,k+1}$ can be discontinuous at the crack tip because they are null in the uncracked zone $y \geq a$.

Besides, in equation (13), we identify the linear density of the individual strain energy release rates related to modes I, II and III, respectively defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} g_I(x) &= \frac{1}{2 \times l} v^{k,k+1}(x, a^+) \gamma_3^{k,k+1}(x, a^-), \quad g_{II} = \frac{1}{2 \times l} \tau_2^{k,k+1}(x, a^+) \gamma_2^{k,k+1}(x, a^-) \text{ and} \\ g_{III} &= \frac{1}{2 \times l} \tau_1^{k,k+1}(x, a^+) \gamma_1^{k,k+1}(x, a^-). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

At this step, if a delamination criterion involving the individual strain energy release rates is used, the interfacial stresses and the displacement discontinuities at the crack tip must be calculated. In order to determine a simpler criterion expression, the interfacial displacement discontinuities at the crack tip are determined as linear algebraic functions of the interfacial stresses calculated at the crack tip. This task is done by writing the constitutive equations ahead of the crack tip and behind the crack tip and by making use of the continuity on $y=a$ of the generalized displacements defined in equations (4). The individual strain energy release rates become then

$$\begin{aligned} g_I &= \frac{1}{l} \psi_3 \left(\left[v^{k,k+1}(x, a^-) \right]^+ \right)^2, \quad g_{II} = \frac{1}{l} \left[\psi_{22} \left(\tau_2^{k,k+1}(x, a^-) \right)^2 + \psi_{21} \tau_1^{k,k+1}(x, a^-) \tau_2^{k,k+1}(x, a^-) \right], \\ g_{III} &= \frac{1}{l} \left[\psi_{11} \left(\tau_1^{k,k+1}(x, a^-) \right)^2 + \psi_{12} \tau_1^{k,k+1}(x, a^-) \tau_2^{k,k+1}(x, a^-) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where $\left[v^{k,k+1}(x, a^-) \right]^+$ is the positive part of $v^{k,k+1}(x, a^-)$, where ψ_3 and $\psi_{\alpha\beta}$ are scalar constants given by basic matrix calculations, their values do not depend on the crack growth but depend on the position of the cracked interface, on the material properties and on the stacking sequence. Besides, the analytical calculations prove that $\psi_3 > 0$.

The calculation of the interfacial stresses at the crack tip and equations (15) yield the values of the individual strain energy release rates for a given position of the delamination front $y = a$. These expressions are valid even at delamination onset. This is one of the advantages of these equations because no displacement discontinuities and no initial flaws have to be considered for calculating the strain energy release rates at delamination initiation. In this manner, equations (15) can help predict delamination onset and growth in a brittle elastic multi-layer by means of an adequate delamination criterion.

DELAMINATION CRITERION

Any fracture criterion for a brittle elastic material can involve the strain energy release rates associated to a crack. For homogeneous isotropic materials, one single material parameter, the critical strain energy release rate is enough to predict the crack growth. For multi-layered composite materials, a delamination criterion based on the total strain energy release rate is not adequate [8]. It is necessary to separate the contribution of each fracture mode (the individual strain energy release rates) on the total energy release rate. A general criterion can be expressed as follows:

$$f \left(\frac{G_I}{G_I^c}, \frac{G_{II}}{G_{II}^c}, \frac{G_{III}}{G_{III}^c} \right) \geq 1 \quad (16)$$

where the function f and the constant parameters G_I^c , G_{II}^c and G_{III}^c must be identified by means of experimental data. This task is difficult to be carried out completely. Several authors have contributed to the progress of this task for some materials. In this section, the G_{III}^c parameter is identified for carbon-epoxy laminates using results of edge delamination tests (EDT) [4,18] and evaluations of the $M4-5N$ interfacial stresses at delamination onset. The criterion provides very accurate delamination

onset predictions for the considered tested laminates, as well as the criterion proposed in [3,4] and based on the maximum values of the interfacial shear stresses of the $M4-5N$ model. The reason of the accuracy of the criterion involving the maximum interfacial stresses is found by analysing the analytical expression of the strain energy release rates.

1 Mode III delamination onset criterion for carbon-epoxy laminates

EDT tests with $(\pm 10_n)_s$ and $(\pm 20_n)_s$ laminates are classical tensile tests for identifying mode III delamination onset criteria [1,2,3,4]. For these laminates delamination appears at the edges at the 10/-10 and 20/-20 interfaces (see Figure 2). Herein, the experimental results in [4] and [18] are used in order to determine a delamination onset criterion based on the strain energy release rate calculations. The unidirectional carbon-epoxy materials used for elaborating the laminates were the T700/CTE1-15 in [4] and the T800/914 in [18]. The measured overall tensile stresses σ at delamination onset vs. the number of plies n are displayed in Figures 3 and 4 for the T700/CTE1-15 and for the T800/914 laminates, respectively. An important thickness effect on delamination onset is revealed. Moreover, the overall laminates behavior is almost linear elastic before delamination onset [4,18]. This justifies the use of linear elastic fracture mechanics.

Figure 2. $(\pm 10_n)_s$ and $(\pm 20_n)_s$ laminates subjected to a tensile loading

Figure 3. Critical loads for T700/CTE1-15 laminates: predictions and tests

Figure 4. Critical loads for T800/914 laminates: predictions and tests

Let us determine the strain energy release rates related to the delamination cracks in these laminates. First, it is necessary to evaluate the stress and displacement fields in the laminate. Owing to symmetries and assuming a uniform stress and strain state along the x -axis, the problem can be reduced to the analysis of the shaded quarter section in Figure 2. In this simplified problem, one single crack is to be considered and following the same method as in section 4, the $M4-5N$ equations lead to the following expression of the strain energy release rates for a unit length (see equation (15)) and for each delamination crack:

$$G_I = \lambda_3 \left(\left[V^{n,n+1} \right]^+ \right)^2, \quad G_{II} = \lambda_{22} \left(\tau_2^{n,n+1} \right)^2 + \lambda_{21} \tau_1^{n,n+1} \tau_2^{n,n+1}, \quad G_{III} = \lambda_{11} \left(\tau_1^{n,n+1} \right)^2 + \lambda_{12} \tau_1^{n,n+1} \tau_2^{n,n+1} \quad (17)$$

where λ_{11} , λ_{12} , λ_{21} , λ_{22} and λ_3 are scalar constants calculated analytically and depend on the number of layers n , on the material elastic properties and a priori on the θ angle of the $(\pm\theta)_s$ laminate ($\theta = 10$ and 20); $\nu^{n,n+1}$, $\tau_1^{n,n+1}$ and $\tau_2^{n,n+1}$ are the interfacial stresses at the $\theta/-\theta$ interface calculated just ahead of the crack tip ($\nu^{n,n+1} = \sigma_{zz}$, $\tau_1^{n,n+1} = \tau_{xz}$, $\tau_2^{n,n+1} = \tau_{yz}$). When the crack length is tended to zero, one obtains the strain energy release rates at delamination initiation. The calculation of the interfacial stresses $\nu^{n,n+1}$, $\tau_1^{n,n+1}$ and $\tau_2^{n,n+1}$ at the free edge of the uncracked laminate yields then the strain energy release rates at delamination onset.

In order to evaluate the interfacial stresses in the tested laminates, the software DEILAM [7] is used. This software makes a semi-analytical resolution of the free edge problem for a given overall tensile strain based on the *M4-5N* equations. Since no singularities appear in the model the software computations converge quickly. For the calculations, each physical ply is modelled by a ‘‘model layer’’ in order to reproduce the thickness effect; in [3,4,19] this modelling is justified by the fact that a failure criterion of brittle materials must be associated to a reference material volume. Calculations show that normal stresses $\nu^{n,n+1}$ at the edge (thus at the crack tip at delamination onset) are negative and that all of the interfacial stresses can be neglected except the shear stresses $\tau_{xz} = \tau_1^{n,n+1}$ at the $10/-10$ and $20/-20$ interfaces of the $(\pm 10)_s$ and $(\pm 20)_s$ laminates, respectively. The calculation of the strain energy release rates in all of the possible positions of the cracked interface explains why delamination appears at the $\theta/-\theta$ interfaces. Moreover, the only term to be considered in equations (17) is $\lambda_{11}(\tau_1^{n,n+1})^2$ and the only strain energy release rate to be determined is thus

$$G_{III} \approx \lambda_{11}(\tau_1^{n,n+1})^2. \quad (18)$$

In this manner, equation (18) and the evaluated interfacial stresses yield the strain energy release rates predicted by the model for the T700/CTE1-15 laminates and for the T800/914 laminates at delamination onset. For each material type, calculations show that the strain energy release rates at delamination onset are almost the same for all of the laminates. Let us choose the following delamination criterion:

$$G_{III} = G_{III}^c \quad (19)$$

where G_{III} is the mode III strain energy release rate and G_{III}^c is the average of the calculated strain energy release rates at delamination onset: 196J/m^2 for the T700/CTE1-15 and 208J/m^2 for the T800/914. By making use of this criterion, of the theoretical strain energy release rates for a given overall tensile strain and of the linear elastic behavior assumption, the theoretical overall tensile strain that should lead to delamination can be calculated for each coupon. The multiplication of these values by the overall Young’s Modulus in the coupons length direction yield the theoretical tensile stress σ at delamination onset. For each material, the critical theoretical loads σ and the experimental loads are displayed in Figures 3 and 4 for the different values of the number n of plies. The experimental scale effects are well reproduced and the theoretical predictions are very accurate. The error committed by our predictions are smaller than 5.5% for the T700-CTE1-15 and smaller than 15.1% for the T800/914.

An important remark

The critical mode III strain energy release rate G_{III}^c for each material identified above depends on the thickness of the ‘‘model ply’’. If the ply thickness changes, a new identification must be performed. In this manner, the mode III strain energy release rate G_{III}^c is not an intrinsic material property. This value depends on the modelling but it proves to be a relevant parameter to predict delamination initiation.

2 Validation of a maximum stress criterion of delamination onset

In [3,4], an empirical criterion was proposed for predicting mode III delamination initiation in the same laminates considered above. This criterion involves the maximum values (the edge values) of the interfacial shear stresses τ_{xz} evaluated by DEILAM. This criterion is expressed as follows:

$$\tau_{xz} = \tau^c \quad (20)$$

where τ_{xz} is the interfacial shear stress and τ^c is the critical shear stress (a constant that depends on the material and on the thickness of the “model layer” used to evaluate the interfacial stresses by DEILAM). The values of the critical shear stress are 265 MPa [4] and 240 MPa [3] for the T700/CTE1-15 and the T800/914 respectively. The maximum stress criterion reproduce well the thickness effect and yield very accurate predictions, the same as the criterion based on the strain energy release rate calculations. At this step, it is interesting to find the deep reasons of the prediction accuracy of this maximum stress criterion.

The strain energy release rate G_{III} per unit length at delamination onset has the expression written in equation (18). Let us calculate the values of the coefficient λ_{11} appearing in this equation for the $(\pm 10_n)_s$ and $(\pm 20_n)_s$ laminates and for the two carbon-epoxy materials. As seen in Table 1, for each material the values of the coefficient λ_{11} depend little on the angle and on the number of plies, this means that they are practically constant. Let us define the average λ_{III} of the values of λ_{11} for each material ($\lambda_{III} = 2.79 \times 10^{-15} m^4/J$ and $\lambda_{III} = 3.75 \times 10^{-15} m^4/J$ for the T700/CTE1-15 and T800/914, respectively). In this manner, the criterion

$$G_{III}^c = G_{III} \approx \lambda_{III} \tau_{xz}^2 \quad (21)$$

is quasi-equivalent to the maximum stress criterion written in (20), and thus

$$\tau^c \approx \sqrt{\frac{G_{III}^c}{\lambda_{III}}} \quad (22)$$

One can verify the validity of this equation introducing the values of the terms for each material. This validates the maximum stress criterion from an energetic point of view.

λ_{11} coefficient (m^4/J)	T700/CTE1-15 laminates		T800/914 laminates	
	$(\pm 10_n)_s$	$(\pm 20_n)_s$	$(\pm 10_n)_s$	$(\pm 20_n)_s$
$n = 1$	2.91	2.91	3.86	4.02
$n = 2$	2.75	2.75	3.65	3.79
$n = 3$	2.75	2.75	3.64	3.79
$n = 4$	2.75	2.75	3.64	3.79
$n = 5$			3.64	3.79
$n = 8$			3.64	

Table 1. λ_{11} coefficients for the different laminates (m^4/J)

CONCLUSION

In this paper the analytical expression of the individual strain energy release rates in a delaminated multi-layer have been determined by making use of a model of elastic plates called *M4-5N* which takes into account discontinuous displacements at the delaminated interfaces. The authors apply the VCCT and the interfacial constitutive equations and express the individual strain energy release rates as quadratic functions of the interfacial stresses at the crack tip. In this manner, the strain energy release rates can be calculated at delamination onset without the well known assumption of an initial flaw length. This theoretical result can help predict delamination onset and growth in multi-layers even with a high number of layers by means of a relevant delamination criterion. As an

application example, the authors have determined a mode III delamination criterion on the strain energy release rates using data of edge delamination tests on laminates made up of two types of carbon-epoxy composites. This criterion predicts accurately delamination onset for the considered laminates as well as the empirical maximum stress criteria in [3,4]. The analysis of the analytical expressions of the two types of criteria validates the empirical criteria from an energetic point of view.

The analytical expression of the individual strain energy release rates presented herein is an important progress in the prediction of delamination onset and growth. In order to reach the main goal, all of the critical individual strain energy release rates and the criterion function for mixed mode loading must be identified by judicious tests. Besides, the determination of the strain energy release rates need the evaluation of the interfacial stresses not only at delamination onset but also when the delamination crack exists. This requires a modification of the software DEILAM [7] which will be presented in a subsequent paper. The integration of the analytical results presented herein into the modified version of DEILAM will help calculate the strain energy release rates in delaminated laminates even in the presence of a high number of layers.

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